

DEVELOPMENT OF REFORMS IN THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS LEGAL FRAMEWORK OVER THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract. This article analyzes the reforms carried out in the healthcare system during the years of independence of Uzbekistan and the creation of a regulatory framework for the development of this area, as well as their significance through historical literature and archival sources. Also, the results of reforms in the health care system created in the country, existing problems are scientifically studied.

Index Terms: Constitution, article 40, health, sanitary control, immunity, pharmaceuticals, insurance, prevention, care, RMC.

1. Cost:

Since the year of independence of Uzbekistan, in order to restore the health of the population, the country began to implement the policy of fundamental reform of the health care system. From the first years of the period of reforming the healthcare system, the issues of reforming this system and creating its legal basis were developed. Today, the study and research of the history of the health care system, the introduction of reforms in this regard, the scientific analysis of the processes of solving existing problems are of urgent importance in the study of the history of this field in Uzbekistan.

2. Methods:

The article is presented on the basis of generally recognized methods such as historical comparison, systematization, and analytical conclusions, in which the processes and results of the reform of the health care system and the creation of its legal foundations in Uzbekistan from the first years of independence were studied.

3. Research results:

When Uzbekistan gained its independence, the creation of new reforms in the health system and its legal basis, like all other sectors in the country, became one of the important tasks of the day. In order to implement these, first of all, it was necessary to develop legislation related to health care. In order to implement these processes, first of all, articles related to this field were included in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to him, in Article 48 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Everyone has the right to maintain health and use qualified medical services" [1. P. 12] was defined as. In order to develop the healthcare system in Uzbekistan, a general program for 1996-1998 was developed and approved in March 1992 at the meeting of the Ministry of Health. On January 14, 1999, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted the decision "On improving the management of the health care system of the Republic of Uzbekistan", and these documents determined the ways of reforms to be implemented in the health care system of the country. Also, in the years of independence, several laws related to the health sector were adopted; On July 14, 1991 "On

Prevention of AIDS", on July 3, 1992 "On State Sanitary Control", on December 9, 1992 "On Compulsory Treatment of Patients Suffering from Chronic Alcoholism, Drug Addiction or Poisoning", on August 29, 1996 "On Citizen Health on storage", on April 25, 1997 "On drugs and pharmaceutical activities", on November 10, 1998 "On the state program of reforming the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan", August 19, 1999 "On Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances", August 19, 1999 "On Prevention of Human Immunodeficiency Virus Infection (HIV)", August 31, 2000 "On Psychiatric Care", May 11, 2001 "Remove the Population" "On prevention of iodine deficiency diseases", August 30, 2002 "On donation of blood and its components", "On prevention of iodine deficiency diseases" on May 3, 2007, "On prevention of micronutrient deficiency among the population" on June 7, 2010.

Based on these adopted laws, the concept of the healthcare system and the tasks that need to be implemented in the country were determined [2. P. 28]. In order to develop and develop the financing of this sector, the process of dividing medical services into paid and free services was carried out during the implementation of health sector reforms. According to it, legal and physical entities started providing paid services with funds, and free services were allocated by the state budget. These reforms in the development of the industry in the country created the need to train not only qualified knowledge, but also management and marketing personnel, which led to problems in the training of managers in the country.

In this way, reforms in the healthcare system, like reforms in other areas, began to be implemented step by step. The originality of the health care reform is shown by the fact that it was aimed at changing health care activities at the horizontal level in Uzbekistan at the initial stage.

In the early period of independence, there was a need to develop national programs in the country. According to it, the tasks of the implementation of the national program developed according to it were determined, according to which, first of all, the protection of mother and child health, the organization of medical assistance to the population in the prevention of infectious diseases, tuberculosis, tumors and sexually transmitted diseases, and the improvement of the qualifications of medical science and medical personnel, providing health care with funds and carrying out economic reforms, providing treatment and prevention institutions with medicines, etc. were determined.

As a result of the above-mentioned Decree No. 2107 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on November 10, 1998 "On the State Program for the Reform of the Healthcare System of the Republic of Uzbekistan", departments in the field of "Higher Nursing" have been operating in all medical institutions of our Republic since the 1999-2000 academic year. began to be shown [5. P. 3]. By 2007, the master's course in this direction began its activity.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 2107 "On the State Program for the Reform of the Health Care System of the Republic of Uzbekistan", he specified the main principles of the system, as well as defining the goals and a number of tasks of reforms in the country [4. P. 10].

The purpose of the implemented reforms was to establish a health care system in the Republic of Uzbekistan that would ensure the preservation and improvement of the population's health, as well as to create conditions for raising a healthy generation. In order to implement these processes in the country, work was organized and carried out based on the above-mentioned principles.

Instead of the previously existing five-level systems in the country, i.e. district central hospital, district hospital, village district hospital, village doctor's outpatient clinic, village paramedic midwifery centers, instead of rural medical centers and central district hospital, a two-level primary medical system was introduced. passed.

On March 18, 2008, Resolution No. 48 of the Cabinet of Ministers on the Regulation "On Village Medical Center" was adopted. According to this Regulation, the procedure for organizing the activities of rural medical centers and their financing was established. It was introduced that the village doctor's office operates as a treatment-prophylactic institution designed to provide primary medical and sanitary assistance to the villagers in the relevant area, etc. In accordance with the regulation, it was envisaged that instead of rural medical centers will be established in rural areas taking into account the population settlement system, the number and distance of settlements, the range of services, the development of the road network, agricultural production and other types of production.

Instead of rural medical centers were established in the form of a state institution and received the status of an independent legal entity. Based on the principles of general practice doctor and family medical and social services, provision of high-quality primary medical and sanitary assistance to rural residents was defined as the goal of the organization of the Instead of rural medical centers and its activities. The following were included in the main tasks of Instead of rural medical centers [4. P. 48];

- providing medical services for the prevention and treatment of the most common diseases to the rural population, both at the level of individual clients and at the level of the whole family;
- to provide timely medical advice, to refer clients to specialized medical institutions for hospitalization in case of rare diseases or severe and atypical variants of the disease course;
- providing emergency medical care to residents of the serviced area in accordance with diagnostic and treatment standards before hospitalization;
- implementation of measures to prevent and reduce illness, injury, disability and death among the population served, etc. [5. P. 48].

In order to implement reforms in the healthcare system in the Republic of Uzbekistan and to further develop them, the development of new economic mechanisms has been started in order to prevent and reduce losses in the society, to use the resources available in the country rationally.

As a result, there was a need to develop new methods of providing medical services in the republic. As a result, rural and urban (neighborhood) medical centers were established to provide effective medical services.

Also, during the years of independence, the projects "Health-1" and "Health-2" were developed. As part of these projects, 70 million US dollars were allocated to further improve the infrastructure of primary medical institutions in rural areas [6. B. 3]. With the involvement of World Bank investments within the framework of the State Program for the Reform of the Health Care System, 3192 instead of rural medical centers in our country within the framework of the "Health-1" and "Health-2" projects in 1998-2011 with a total cost of 76 million dollars, was fully supplied with laboratory equipment [7. P. 8].

Within the framework of the "Health-2" project, 570 dental equipments were delivered to instead of rural medical centers and multidisciplinary polyclinics. In order to improve the provision of cheap and quality medicines to rural residents, social pharmacies were

established in 811 instead of rural medical centers, GSM standard landline phones were installed in 1056 instead of rural medical centers, and the provision of instead of rural medical centers with a communication system reached 97.7% [7. P. 8]

In conclusion, it should be said that since the first years of Uzbekistan's independence, reforms in the health care system, like other sectors, have been raised to the level of state policy. In order to strengthen and develop this sector, the head of the country adopted several legal documents and began to put them into practice. As a result, health centers were renovated and new ones were built. Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.

Also, rural medical centers began to improve their activities. By 2013, the number of rural medical centers and the number and weight of the services provided in them increased. About 3,200 rural medical centers equipped with modern equipment were established. As a result of these processes, qualified medical care is provided to women and children in the most remote districts.

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